

ANALYTICAL MODELLING OF ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF NANOCOMPOSITES WITH A NEW TYPE OF REINFORCEMENT

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1 Introduction

In their paper, Wang et al. [1] reported a new brush-like nano-composition: the CdTe nanowires coated with SiO₂ nanowires, nearly parallel bristles growing perpendicular to the surface. The structure “CdTe nanowire - SiO₂ nanowires” consists of three components: CdTe wire forms the solid core, which is jointed continuously with coating from SiO₂ nanowires in the form of some solid shell, and then the shell is coated periodically by bristled and smooth zones, Fig. 1.

Bristled nanowires can be used for the ultimate purpose of fabricating composite materials with improved fibre-matrix adhesion and hence the increased shear strength. In order to study the effective properties of the entire composite and the effect of reinforcement with bristled nanowires on the overall performance of the material, a four-component model is required - the matrix being the fourth component, in addition to the three components mentioned above.

This paper gives the details of the method for deriving the explicit formulas for effective elastic constants of such materials.

2 Methodology

This work concerns the development of a new four-component model for predicting the mechanical properties of nanocomposites reinforced with bristled nanowires. It generalises the approaches presented in [2-4].

The model assumes that fibres are arranged in the matrix periodically as a quadratic or hexagonal lattice. Then the representative volume element (unit

cell) consists of the matrix and a coated fibre, Fig. 2. At that, the coating itself has several sub-components, which is a new feature of the model: the coated fibre consists of three different parts: a solid core, a solid coating (homogeneous shell), and a “bristled coating” (composite shell). The fourth component in the model is the matrix. A segment of the model representing the core fibre with solid coating and bristles attached to the solid coating is shown in Fig. 3. Subsequently, the following notations are used to distinguish the four components of composite: (1) for the fibre core, (2) for the fibre solid coating, (3) for the fibre bristled coating and (4) for the matrix.

Three out of four components are homogeneous materials, e.g., EPON828 epoxy matrix, SiO₂ solid coating and CdTe solid fibre core, with known properties (Young’s modulus, shear modulus, Poisson’s ratio, density etc.). However, the bristled coating is itself a composite consisting of, e.g., the EPON828 matrix reinforced by SiO₂ nanowires, Figs. 2 and 3. The effective properties of this component are evaluated separately beforehand. The easiest way to do it is by using the classical Voigt and Reuss bounds. For this purpose, we would need to know the diameter and the length of bristles, and their number per unit surface area of microfibres or nanowires. Also, in order to use the known formulas of the rule of mixture, we assume here that all the bristles are parallel to each other, i.e. that the properties of the bristled coating (3), Fig. 2, do not change with the radius. This assumption, being, of course, a certain simplification, seems reasonable, since the length of SiO₂ nanowires used for reinforcement is rather small.

The mathematical formulation of the model is based on considering the four simple states of plane elastic equilibrium of the unit cell (a square with the side l_{unit} , Fig. 4) - i.e. longitudinal tension, transverse tension, longitudinal shear and transverse shear - and using the Muskhelishvili complex potentials [5] for each domain occupied by a separate component. The model yields the explicit formulas for five effective elastic constants.

The possible case of imperfect adhesion between the fibre core and the matrix can be taken into account by considering one of the four components, i.e. the coating layer, with the appropriately reduced properties.

3 Deriving the explicit expressions for effective constants

The procedure of deriving the explicit expressions for effective elastic constants of the suggested four-component structural model is by no means a trivial mathematical exercise. For the lack of space, here it can be given only in outline for one of the constants, namely the shear modulus, G . Hereafter, z is a complex co-ordinate in the transverse cross section, and i is imaginary unit)

The cornerstone of the analytical procedure is the representation of the Muskhelishvili potentials by: a harmonic complex function, which is regular in the domain of fibre core (circle $A^{(1)}$ in Fig. 4):

$$\varphi_{(1)}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{2k}^{(1)} \frac{z^{2k+1}}{2k+1} \quad (1)$$

a function in the form of Laurent series, which is regular in the domain of fibre solid coating (ring $A^{(2)}$ in Fig. 4):

$$\varphi_{(2)}(z) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} a_{2k}^{(2)} z^{2k+1} \quad (2)$$

a function in the form of Laurent series, which is regular in the domain of fibre bristle coating (ring $A^{(3)}$ in Fig. 4):

$$\varphi_{(3)}(z) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} a_{2k}^{(3)} z^{2k+1} \quad (3)$$

a doubly-periodic function constructed utilising the Weierstrass functions in the domain of the matrix ($A^{(4)}$ in Fig. 4):

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{(4)}(z) = & \\ & + a_0^{(4)} z - \lambda^2 a_2^{(4)} \left(\frac{1}{z} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \alpha_{n,0} \frac{z^{2n+1}}{2n+1} \right) \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_{2k+2}^{(4)} \lambda^{2k+2} \alpha_{n,k} \frac{z^{2n+1}}{2n+1} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_{2k+2}^{(4)} \lambda^{2k+2}}{(2k+1)z^{2k+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha_{n,k}$ are the constants used in the theory of Weierstrass functions, $\lambda = 2r_{(3)}/l_{unit}$, and $a_{2k}^{(1)}$, $a_{2k}^{(2)}$, $a_{2k}^{(3)}$, $a_{2k}^{(4)}$ are the yet unknown coefficients in the series given by Eqs. (1)-(4).

Then the averaged stresses and strains for each of the domains are calculated using the contour integrals, Fig 5. This procedure results in the following expression for the effective longitudinal shear modulus of entire four-component composition, G^* :

$$\begin{aligned} G^* = G_{12}^* = & [G_{(4)} c^{(4)} + 2c^{(3)} + c^{(4)} G_{(4)} G_{(3)}^{-1} \\ & + 4c^{(2)} (1 + G_{(3)} G_{(2)}^{-1})^{-1} \\ & + 8c^{(1)} (1 + G_{(3)} G_{(2)}^{-1})^{-1} (1 + G_{(2)} G_{(1)}^{-1})^{-1}] \\ & \times [c^{(4)} + (2 - c^{(4)}) G_{(4)} G_{(3)}^{-1}] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $c^{(1)}$, $c^{(2)}$, $c^{(3)}$ and $c^{(4)}$ are the volume fractions of the fibre core, the fibre solid coating, the fibre bristled coating and the matrix, respectively.

Eq. (5) yields the well-known formulas for two-component and three-component models as the particular cases, see [3,4]. The latter will follow from Eq. (5) if the volume fraction of bristled coating $c^{(3)} = 0$ and the shear moduli of bristled, $G_{(3)}$, and solid, $G_{(2)}$, coatings are the same; the former will follow from Eq. (5) if, additionally, the volume fraction of solid coating $c^{(2)} = 0$ and the shear moduli of solid coating, $G_{(2)}$, and fibre core, $G_{(1)}$, are the same.

Similarly, the explicit expressions for other four effective constants for the entire four-component composition are deduced.

4 Results

The values of all five effective elastic constants representing the transversely-isotropic response of the entire composite were computed by the method outlined in the previous section. The results for composites reinforced by the bristled nanowires

show that the properties in longitudinal direction are the most sensitive to the density of bristles. The increase in the number of bristles per unit surface of the fibres gives a very strong rise to the value of Young's modulus. However, the shear modulus, being the driving parameter for the strength estimation of the entire composition [3,4], is less sensitive to this factor. The difference between the values of shear modulus for the considered cases of sparse, medium, and dense density of bristles is less than 2.5%.

In the same time, the presence of bristled fibres itself – either with dense, medium, or sparse density of bristles – gives the significant increase in the shear modulus in composites if compared with the case without bristles. In the considered examples, the increase in the shear modulus from 1.4 times in the case of sparse reinforcement to 2 times in the case of dense reinforcement was achieved (depending on the volume fraction of the matrix) [3,4].

As a next step, after gathering the necessary experimental data, the effective properties for various practical nanocomposites can be computed using the proposed four-component model.

5 Discussion

Undoubtedly, even after verification of predicted properties for bristled nanowires by comparing them with the results of specially designed experiments, the suggested approach can be considered as merely the first step towards modelling bristled nanowires and their application. Even a four-component model is an idealisation of the complex internal structure of the considered materials. However, it can provide us with important insight into some basic relationships between the properties of constituents and the overall performance of such materials.

Ultimately, any mechanics of materials, including mechanics of nanomaterials, envisages analysis of materials for structural applications, be it on macro-, micro- or nanoscale [2-4]. It is therefore a logical conclusion that any research on nanomaterials should be followed by the analysis of nanomaterials working in various structures and devices. Micro- and nano-structural applications look like the most natural and promising areas of the nanomaterials utilisation. They do not require large industrial production of nanoparticles which are currently rather expensive.

It seems pertinent to recall a discussion on mechanical properties of new materials which took place more than 40 years ago. In the concluding remarks, Bernal [6] said: "Here we must reconsider our objectives. We are talking about new materials but ultimately we are interested, not so much in materials themselves, but in the structures in which they have to function." The authors believe that nanomechanics faces the same challenges that micromechanics did 40 years ago, which Professor Bernal described so eloquently.

6 Conclusions

This paper presents a new four-component model for predicting the mechanical properties of nanocomposites reinforced with bristled nanowires. The mathematical formulation of the model is based on using the Muskhelishvili complex potentials for each domain occupied by a separate component. The effective elastic constants are computed for different densities of bristles.

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Fig.1. The brush-like CdTe-MSA – SiO₂ nanostructure [1].

Fig.2. Schematic of the model.

Fig.3. A segment of the model: core fibre with solid coating and bristles attached to the solid coating.

Fig.4. The unit cell of the model.

Fig.5. Contours used for evaluation of integrals.

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